

Conversion of Abandoned Tree Covered Permanent Grassland

www.af4eu.eu

Animal grazing helps convert abandoned tree-covered permanent grassland into productive agroforestry systems

Slovakia has approximately 2.4 million ha of agricultural land of which 0.85 million ha are permanent grassland. Approximately one third (more than 30 %) of the area of permanent grassland is unused, abandoned and overgrown with shrubs and trees in various stages of succession (so-called "white areas") and these areas are mostly withdrawn from agricultural land for the subsidy system. In recent years, the interest of owners and farmers in using such areas for pasture production has increased significantly, which is also related to their efforts to include these areas in the subsidy system. Currently, the common practise in Slovakia is the so-called revitalisation – the restoration of the original state through recultivation measures, during which all woody vegetation is removed from such areas. Another option, which is currently strongly favoured due to climate change but not yet officially applied in Slovakia, is the conversion of these areas into productive agroforestry silvopastoral systems – grazing areas while retaining some of the existing trees or shrubs. Since 2022, the National Forest Centre has been implementing the project "Models of transformation of tree-covered non-forest land into productive agroforestry systems (TRANSAGROLES)" within which 3 pilot research and demonstration plots representing "white areas" of lowland (Bojnice), hilly (Betliar) and mountainous (Liptovská Teplička) areas of Slovakia have been established. These plots will serve for long-term research of multiple aspects (technical, environmental and social) of this transformation and will also serve as examples of good practice.

**Michal Pástor, Jaroslav
Jankovič**

National Forest Centre, Slovakia

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.